

Original Article

Extraction of Vegetable Oil from Rice Husk and Synthesis of Fatty Acid Monoglycerides

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ABSTRACT

Rice husk, an abundant waste from the agro-industrial sector, contains residual vegetable oil rich in unsaturated fatty acids. In this study, an eco-friendly and efficient strategy is presented for converting rice husk biomass into monoglycerides, compounds of significant industrial importance. The process begins with extraction of rice husk in a semi-automatic Soxhlet apparatus (ASV-6M) using ethyl acetate, which demonstrated the highest extraction efficiency among six tested solvents, yielding up to 2.82% oil from rice husk. The extracted oil was subjected to a catalytic glycerolysis reaction under moderate pressure and temperature conditions (220 °C for 4 h) in the presence of KOH, resulting in a monoglyceride content of approximately 68.87%. The obtained mixture was purified using a two-step method involving crystallization in an acetone-water solution, followed by column chromatography on silica gel, which afforded monoglycerides with a purity of up to 93%. Structural and compositional analyses were carried out by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and infrared (IR) spectroscopy, confirming the presence of key esters such as monoglycerides of palmitic and oleic acids. Mass spectrometry data confirmed the molecular weights corresponding to the structures of the monoglycerides, while the IR spectra showed characteristic absorption bands corresponding to ester and hydroxyl functional groups.

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

Introduction

Sustainable utilization of agro-industrial waste has become one of the most important directions in modern green chemistry and food technologies. Among the abundant agricultural residues, rice husk accounts for about 20% of global rice production, amounting to more than 150 million tons annually [1]. Traditionally treated as waste or used for low-value applications such as fuel, rice husk has recently attracted attention due to its rich biochemical composition, including silica [2], cellulose [3], and oil fractions [4].

The lipid content of rice husk represents a valuable feedstock for the production of glycerides with diverse industrial applications [5]. Monoglycerides are widely employed in the food, pharmaceutical, and cosmetic industries as emulsifiers, stabilizers, and bioactive compounds. They improve texture, shelf life, and structural stability of products while remaining safe for human consumption [6].

According to the study in [7], rice husk contains up to 21.44% crude oil, mainly composed of oleic (48%), linoleic (35%), and palmitic (14%) acids. Traditional monoglyceride production often relies on refined vegetable oils [8]. For instance, in [9], an eco-friendly method for obtaining monoglycerides from ethyl esters of linseed oil via alkaline glycerolysis was developed. Using NaOH as a catalyst at 130 °C, a monoglyceride yield of up to 76% was achieved with almost complete conversion of the starting esters. This

work highlights the potential of biodiesel-derived esters as intermediates in the production of biofunctional lipids.

In [7], glycerolysis under supercritical carbon dioxide conditions was investigated using soybean, sunflower, and corn oils. The process resulted in high conversion with monoglyceride yields of up to 49%, while the applied conditions (250 °C, 20 MPa) eliminated the need for organic solvents, ensuring the eco-friendliness of the process. The authors of [10] reported the synthesis of mono- and diglycerides through glycerolysis of vegetable oils using solid heterogeneous catalysts such as calcium and magnesium oxides. The results showed that CaO can effectively catalyse the reaction at 220 °C, providing high monoglyceride yields without the use of solvents. In [11,12], monoglyceride synthesis was described using ionic liquids as catalysts. The use of ionic liquids enabled yields exceeding 69% at 200 °C, with the advantages of avoiding volatile solvents and reusability of the catalyst.

In this study, a circular-economy-based approach was proposed involving the extraction of rice husk oil and its conversion into mono- and diglycerides through catalytic glycerolysis [13]. The process was optimized to achieve high selectivity and product yield by employing accessible solvents, mild reaction conditions, and scalable purification steps. The resulting bioemulsifiers have potential applications as sustainable alternatives to synthetic ingredients, contributing to waste valorization and environmental protection.

The chemical composition of rice husk varies depending on the cultivation region, climate, and processing methods. Rice husk mainly consists of cellulose, lignin, and amorphous silica. On average, it contains 30–35% cellulose, 10–25% hemicellulose, 15–25% lignin, 1–5% oils and waxes, and 15–20% mineral ash. The silica content in the ash can reach 80–95%, making it an important source of silicate raw materials [2]. The high silica content is a distinctive feature of rice husk compared to other plant residues.

Applications of rice husk are diverse. It is used as a biofertilizer, in the production of construction materials (bricks and concrete) and activated carbon, as well as an adsorbent for water purification [14,15]. Moreover, it is also utilized for bioethanol production and as a fuel due to its lignin and cellulose content [3,16].

About disposal, the high silica content makes natural degradation of rice husk difficult. Therefore, its further utilization, particularly conversion into ash by thermal treatment, is considered the most effective solution [15]. Currently, special attention is given to eco-friendly methods for extracting valuable organic components from rice husk, which is especially relevant in the context of the circular bioeconomy. The content of cellulose, lignin, and hemicellulose makes rice husk suitable for biodegradation and bioethanol synthesis [3,16]. Amorphous silica constitutes 80–95% of the mineral ash, making rice husk a valuable raw material for silica production [2].

The most efficient extraction methods include solvent extraction, supercritical fluid extraction, and ultrasonic extraction [17]. The advantage of Soxhlet extraction is its high reproducibility and the ability to completely recover lipophilic fractions [18]. Oils derived from rice husk contain phenolic antioxidants, sterols, and tocopherols, which possess antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities [19-20].

Experimental

For the extraction of organic compounds, the laboratory Soxhlet method was employed using six organic solvents: acetone, hexane, chloroform,

ethyl acetate, xylene, and benzene. The mass of rice husks was 30 g. The solvent volume was 250 mL. The extraction was carried out at the boiling point of each solvent for 5 hours.

After extraction, the solvent was removed using a rotary evaporator, and the extract was weighed. The yield was calculated according to the formula:

$$\text{Yield (\%)} = (\text{mass of extract} / \text{mass of sample}) \times 100$$

For the extraction of oils from rice husk, the agro-industrial residue was washed, dried, and ground. A 30 g portion of the ground rice husk was weighed and placed into a Soxhlet extractor. Organic solvents (250 mL) were added to a 500 mL round-bottom flask. The extraction process was carried out at the boiling point of each solvent for 5 hours. The obtained results are presented in Table 1. Among the tested solvents, ethyl acetate demonstrated the highest extraction yield.

Glycerolysis Reaction

The extracted rice husk oil (50 g) was reacted with glycerol (25 g) in the presence of 0.75 g of catalyst (CaO, NaOH, or KOH) in a 200 mL autoclave-type reactor. The mixture was purged with nitrogen and heated to 220 °C under continuous stirring for 4 hours. After completion of the reaction, the mixture was cooled to 160 °C, and 1.25 mL of phosphoric acid was added to neutralize the excess base and precipitate impurities. The resulting suspension was filtered and decanted to separate the unreacted glycerol.

Purification of Monoglycerides

The reaction mixture containing monoglycerides, diglycerides, and triglycerides was dissolved in acetone and water (3:1, v/v) and cooled to 5–10 °C for selective precipitation. Diglycerides and triglycerides were removed by filtration. The monoglyceride-enriched solution was further purified by silica gel column chromatography using chloroform as the eluent, yielding high-purity monoglyceride fractions (up to 93%).

Analytical Methods

Gas chromatographic analysis was carried out using an Agilent 7890A/5975C gas chromatograph-mass spectrometer (USA). Chromatographic conditions: mobile phase (carrier gas) – helium; injector temperature 325 °C, split ratio 1,000:1; oven temperature program: initial 50 °C (1 min), ramp 5 °C/min to 280 °C, held for 5 min; total analysis time 53 min. The mass detector operated in electron impact ionization mode. Capillary chromatographic column HP-5MS, 30 m length, 0.25 mm internal diameter, stationary phase – 95% polydimethylsiloxane and 5% phenylmethylpolysiloxane.

FTIR spectra were recorded using an IR-Prestige 21 spectrometer (Shimadzu, Japan, 2008) in the wavelength range of 400–4,000 cm^{-1} without

special sample preparation, employing a DuraSampl IR II attenuated total reflectance (ATR) accessory with single reflection (diamond crystal on ZnSe substrate) from Smiths (USA).

Results and Discussion

Efficiency of Extraction

Among the tested solvents, the highest extraction efficiency was demonstrated by ethyl acetate (2.82%), followed by acetone (2.21%) and chloroform (2.12%). Non-polar solvents such as hexane and benzene showed lower yields. These results indicate that ethyl acetate promotes effective dissolution of lipid components due to its moderate polarity and favourable boiling point.

Table 1: The yield of the substance in different solvents

No.	Solvent	Weight of rice husk (g)	Solvent volume (mL)	The mass of the obtained substance (g)	Output of voluminous substance (%)
1	Ethyl Acetate	30	250	0.8454	2.821
2	Acetone	30	250	0.6617	2.206
3	Chloroform	30	250	0.6348	2.116
4	Hexane	30	250	0.5421	1.807
5	Xylene	30	250	0.5403	1.801
6	Benzene	30	250	0.4886	1.628

The obtained vegetable oil was analyzed using an IR spectrometer (Figure 1). The IR spectrum confirmed the presence of triglyceride esters, showing all characteristic absorption bands. A strong carbonyl stretch (C=O) of the ester group was observed at 1,743 cm^{-1} . Additional key bands included the asymmetric C-O-C stretch at approximately 1,240 cm^{-1} and the strong C-O stretch at 1,161 cm^{-1} . The spectrum also showed stretches indicative of long aliphatic chains: asymmetric and symmetric C-H stretches of $-\text{CH}_2-$ groups at approximately 2,925 and 2,855 cm^{-1} , respectively, and a weak =C-H stretch near 3,010 cm^{-1} , consistent with the presence of unsaturated fatty acids as reported in the literature [7].

Glycerolysis

The glycerolysis process is a reversible reaction between triglycerides and glycerol, leading to the formation of mono- and diglycerides. The key parameters influencing the selectivity and yield of the target products include temperature, reaction time, molar ratio of reactants, and type of catalyst. In this study, three major alkaline catalysts were tested: calcium hydroxide ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$), sodium hydroxide (NaOH), and potassium hydroxide (KOH). Each catalyst exhibits different basicity, solubility, and catalytic activity, which affect the kinetics and equilibrium of the reaction.

Glycerolysis was carried out at 220 °C for 4 hours with an oil-to-glycerol molar ratio of 2:1 and a catalyst loading of 1.5 wt%. All reactions were

performed in a sealed autoclave reactor under nitrogen purging to prevent oxidation.

The catalytic performance of the alkaline catalysts followed the order: KOH > CaO > NaOH. Potassium hydroxide (KOH) demonstrated the highest efficacy, yielding up to 68.87% monoglycerides. This superior activity can be

attributed to its high solubility in the polar reaction medium (glycerol), which ensures homogeneous dispersion and maximizes the accessibility of its strong basic sites to the triglyceride molecules, facilitating efficient nucleophilic attack and cleavage of ester bonds [21].

Figure 1: IR spectrum of vegetable oil obtained by extraction from rice husk

Interestingly, calcium oxide (CaO), a heterogeneous catalyst, exhibited significant activity (67.44%), performing nearly on par with KOH. This can be explained by its strong surface basicity and the formation of calcium diglyceroxide ($\text{Ca}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{O}_3)_2$) *in situ* upon reaction with glycerol. Calcium diglyceroxide is a highly active species that enhances glycerol solubility in the oil phase and effectively catalyzes the glycerolysis reaction [10,22]. While its partial insolubility and tendency to form precipitates complicate product purification, its catalytic potency under these conditions is notable.

In contrast, sodium hydroxide (NaOH) showed the lowest yield (57.68%) among the catalysts tested. Although it is a strong base and operates

homogeneously like KOH, its lower solubility in the oil-glycerol mixture at the reaction temperature may limit its effective concentration and interaction with the reactants. Furthermore, the smaller ionic radius of Na^+ compared to K^+ results in a higher charge density, potentially leading to stronger ion pairing that could slightly reduce the reactivity of the hydroxide anion.

This comparison highlights a trade-off between catalytic performance and process practicality. While KOH offers the highest activity, CaO presents a compelling heterogeneous alternative, mitigating the challenges associated with homogeneous catalyst separation, albeit introducing its own complications in filtration.

Table 2: Yield of monoglyceride after glycerolysis

The catalyst	Rice oil (g)	Glycerol (g)	Mass of catalyst (g)	Yield (%)	Yield (g)	Solvent volume Acetone + water (ml)
CaO	50	25	0,75	67.44	33.72	487.5
NaOH	50	25	0,75	57.68	28.84	487.5
KOH	50	25	0,75	68.87	34.43	487.5

After the completion of the glycerolysis reaction, the resulting reaction mixture represents a complex matrix containing mono-, di- and triglycerides, residual glycerol, traces of solvent, and byproduct impurities. To ensure technological applicability and compliance with food and pharmaceutical industry standards, the target monoacylglycerols (MAGs) must be isolated with a high degree of purity.

The first step of purification was selective crystallization. The reaction mixture was dissolved in an acetone–water solvent system (3:1 V/V), after which the solution was cooled to 5–10 °C. Under these conditions, di- and triglycerides precipitated, while the more polar monoglycerides remained in the solution [23-25]. Filtration allowed the removal of heavy glycerides and mechanical impurities.

The second key step was column chromatography on silica gel, carried out to enhance the degree of purification. For this, a concentrated solution of monoglycerides was applied to a silica gel-packed column and eluted with chloroform under fractional collection control. This method allowed selective separation of lipid fractions due to differences in polarity and adsorption capacity [26].

As a result, a fraction containing up to 93% monoglycerides was obtained, as confirmed by the mass of the collected fractions and subsequent analytical control. Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry confirmed the presence of the main compounds: monoglyceride of palmitic acid and monoglyceride of oleic acid.

Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry was used to analyse the composition of fatty acids and glyceride fractions, with identification of individual molecules based on their mass spectra. Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy was employed to confirm the functional groups of esters and their bonding characteristics.

In the presented chromatogram (GC-MS), two distinct peaks are observed at retention times of 45.0–52.0 min, indicating the presence of two main components in the mixture. The peak at 45 min corresponds to the monoglyceride of palmitic acid. The peak at 47 min corresponds to the monoglyceride of oleic acid, which contains one double bond in the alkyl chain (Figure 2). The absence of significant peaks in the early region (before 40 min) indicates a high purity of the sample from volatile impurities and solvent.

Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis was employed to confirm the structure of the synthesized monoglycerides. The mass spectrum of the first major component (Figure 3) exhibited a molecular ion peak $[M]^+$ at m/z 330.3, which corresponds to the molecular formula $C_{19}H_{38}O_4$ and confirms the identity of glycerol monopalmitate. A predominant fragment ion was observed at m/z 299.3, attributable to the loss of a methoxy radical ($[M - CH_3O]^+$) from the glycerol backbone, a fragmentation pathway well documented for monoglycerides [27].

In the spectrum, intense fragments are observed at m/z 57, 75, and 98, which are characteristic of cleavages along the alkyl chains and the glycerol moiety of the molecule. Peaks at m/z 239 and 257 indicate the presence of fragments containing residues of palmitic acid. The signal at m/z 281 further confirms the presence of a long-chain acyl radical attached to the glycerol backbone.

Thus, the set of registered fragments, including the intense low-mass signals (characteristic of the glycerol moiety) and the heavier peaks (characteristic of the palmitic chain), confirms the formation of palmitic acid monoglyceride. The obtained data are consistent with literature reports on the mass spectra of fatty acid monoglycerides, providing additional confirmation of the structure of the investigated compound.

Figure 2: Chromatogram of a monoglyceride mixture

Figure 3: Mass spectrum of palmitic acid monoglyceride

The mass spectrum of oleic acid monoglyceride (Figure 4) demonstrates characteristic fragments

confirming its structure. The main ion at $m/z = 356.3$ is interpreted as the molecular ion $[M]^+$,

corresponding to the expected molecular mass of compound $C_{21}H_{40}O_4$ (oleic acid monoglyceride). The content of oleic acid monoglyceride was 72.82%. The observed characteristic fragments are as follows: m/z 356 — molecular ion $[M]^+$; m/z 55, 77, 98 — typical fragments of the aliphatic chain (hydrocarbon residues); m/z 137, 165 — fragments containing elements of the glycerol backbone; m/z 221 — ion attributed to the loss of a part of the hydrocarbon chain. Low-intensity peaks in the m/z 280–325 range correspond to larger parts of the molecule or products of secondary fragmentation. The predominant signal at m/z 264 indicates the presence of the intact molecule, and the characteristic distribution of fragments is consistent with the expected fragmentation pattern of oleic acid monoglyceride, thereby confirming the proposed structure.

The molecular masses of the main compounds, determined by MS, corresponded to the expected values.

The obtained spectra (Figure 5) exhibited characteristic peaks confirming the structure of the monoglycerides [27–31]. In the IR spectra of the monoglyceride mixture synthesized from rice oil, the characteristic absorption of carbonyl groups is observed at around $1,735\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and a broad band in the $3000\text{--}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region corresponds to hydroxyl group absorptions.

Thus, the proposed approach combines selective precipitation and efficient chromatographic purification, enabling the production of highly purified monoglycerides suitable for use as emulsifiers in food, pharmaceuticals, and cosmetic products.

Figure 4: Mass spectrum of oleic acid monoglyceride

Figure 5: IR spectrum of the mixture of monoglycerides of palmitic and oleic acids

Conclusion

This study presents a comprehensive and environmentally oriented approach for obtaining functional lipid compounds from agro-industrial waste—rice husks. Soxhlet extraction using various organic solvents demonstrated that ethyl acetate provides the highest oil extraction efficiency, yielding up to 2.82%. The extracted oil contains biologically active compounds and can serve as a valuable feedstock for further chemical transformation.

The next key step was the glycerolysis of the extracted oil, during which the catalytic properties of three bases—CaO, NaOH, and KOH—were investigated. Potassium hydroxide exhibited the highest efficiency, providing a monoglyceride yield of up to 68.87% at 220 °C over a 4-hour reaction period.

To achieve the target product purity, a two-step purification scheme was employed: preliminary selective crystallization using an acetone: water system, followed by column chromatography on silica gel. This approach enabled the isolation of a fraction containing up to 93% monoglycerides,

making it suitable for applications in the food and pharmaceutical industries.

The structural identification and purity assessment were performed using modern analytical techniques, including gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS) and infrared (IR) spectroscopy. The results confirmed the presence of palmitic and oleic acid monoglycerides, meeting quality standards.

Abbreviations

ASV-6M: Automatic Soxhlet Extractor, model 6M
 GC–MS: Gas Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry
 IR: Infrared Spectroscopy
 HP-5MS: High-Performance Capillary Column (5% Phenyl Methylpolysiloxane, used in GC)
 FTIR: Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy
 ATR: Attenuated Total Reflectance
 MAG: Monoacylglyceride

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